

Space, International synergies for resilient communities and ecosystems

Vasco Mantas

Create knowledge.
Foster change.

UT AUSTIN PORTUGAL PROGRAM

UTAustin
Portugal

why space?

○ **global coverage**

○ **detailed views**

○ **high frequency**

○ **time series**

A photograph of a rocket launch at night. The rocket is illuminated from below, and a large, bright plume of fire and smoke is visible at the base. The rocket has several logos, including NASA and the ESA logo. The text "satellites ecosystem sentinels" is overlaid on the right side of the image.

satellites

ecosystem sentinels

forest disturbance

State of Rondônia, Brazil

for scale

forest disturbance

State of Rondônia, Brazil

for scale

forest disturbance

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for scale

forest disturbance

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for scale

forest disturbance

State of Rondônia, Brazil

for scale

forest disturbance

State of Rondônia, Brazil

for scale

1984

1990

2000

2010

2018

subtle and gradual change

Pine Wilt Disease

Pinewood nematode

Pine sawyer beetle

subtle and gradual change

Transnational problem

source

Transnational problem

Con. Portugal: 1999

Spain: 2008

Madeira Isl.: 2009

source

Containment is failing

what if?

what if?

what if?

FOCUS

University of Coimbra | S[&]T | VITO

Horizon 2020 (GA776026 ~2 M eur)

project FOCUS

Plant physiology and nematology

Satellite data analysis

UAV operation

Platform development

Land Use and Land Cover

Climate analysis

End-users

Funding

multi-layered solution

Space (Sentinel/Landsat)

Airborne (APEX)

UAV (multi- hyperspectral)

field and laboratorial analysis

early results

800 spectral samples
monthly lab analysis
machine-learning model

early results

800 spectral samples
monthly lab analysis
machine-learning model
91.6% accuracy

very high resolution

800 m

year 1

year 2

year 3

Open data

End-users engagement

Operational platform

UT Austin Portugal

Thank you

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Contacts

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